

THE LEGAL REGULATION OF LABOR RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article aims to investigate the legal regulation system of labor relation in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Legal regulation of labor relations in Uzbekistan refers to the system of laws and regulations that govern the rights and responsibilities of employers and employees in the country. It encompasses various aspects such as employment contracts, working hours, wages and benefits, occupational safety and health, termination of employment, collective bargaining, and the resolution of labor disputes. The legal regulations aim to establish clear rules and guidelines for employers and employees to follow, ensuring that their rights are respected and their interests are protected.

Keywords: Labor relations, legal regulation, labor code, occupational safety, prevention of exploitation and discrimination.

Labor relations in Uzbekistan are primarily governed by the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was enacted in 1996 and has since undergone several amendments. This code provides a comprehensive framework for the rights and responsibilities of employers and employees, as well as the procedures for resolving labor disputes.

The Labor Code covers various key provisions, including employment contracts, working hours and rest periods, wages and benefits, occupational safety and health, termination of employment, collective bargaining and trade unions, and the resolution of labor disputes [2].

Regarding employment contracts, the code stipulates the necessary elements to be included, such as job description, working hours, wages, and duration of employment. It also regulates fixed-term contracts, probationary periods, and part-time work.

The code establishes standard working hours of 40 hours per week for most employees and provides for rest periods, including daily breaks, weekly rest days, and annual paid leave.

In terms of wages and benefits, the code sets minimum wage requirements determined by the government. It also governs the payment of overtime, bonuses, and other benefits like sick leave and maternity leave.

Occupational safety and health are addressed in the code, outlining the employer's obligations to provide a safe and healthy working environment. This

includes workplace safety measures, accident prevention, and medical examinations.

The code specifies grounds for termination of employment, such as disciplinary reasons, redundancy, or mutual agreement. It also establishes procedures for termination, including notice periods and severance pay [5].

Recognizing the right of employees to form trade unions and engage in collective bargaining, the code allows for the establishment of works councils and regulates the negotiation and enforcement of collective agreements.

To resolve labor disputes, the code provides a system of conciliation, mediation, or arbitration. If these methods fail, employees have the option to seek legal remedies through the courts.

In addition to the Labor Code, there are other laws and regulations that govern specific aspects of labor relations, such as the Law on Employment, the Law on Trade Unions, and various government decrees and resolutions.

The legal regulation of labor relations in Uzbekistan is important for several reasons:

1. Protection of workers' rights: The Labor Code establishes the rights and obligations of employers and employees, ensuring that workers are treated fairly and their rights are protected. This includes provisions for fair wages, working hours, leave entitlements, and social benefits.
2. Promotion of safe and healthy working conditions: The Labor Code includes regulations on workplace safety and protection against accidents and occupational diseases. Employers are required to provide a safe and healthy working environment for their employees, reducing the risk of injuries or illnesses [4].
3. Prevention of exploitation and discrimination: The Labor Code prohibits unfair labor practices, such as discrimination based on gender, age, or disability. It also sets out procedures for addressing grievances and resolving disputes between employers and employees, preventing exploitation or unfair treatment.
4. Promotion of economic stability: By providing a legal framework for labor relations, the Labor Code promotes stability in the labor market. Clear regulations on employment contracts, termination procedures, and collective bargaining help to create a predictable and fair environment for both employers and employees.
5. Facilitation of economic development: A well-regulated labor market can contribute to economic development by attracting investment and fostering

productivity. Employers can have confidence in the legal protections afforded to their workforce, while employees can feel secure in their rights and benefits [3]. Uzbekistan has been actively working to improve its labor legislation in recent years, including the adoption of a new Labor Code in 2019. These changes aim to enhance worker protection, promote decent work, and align the country's labor laws with international standards.

Conclusion. Overall, the legal regulation of labor relations in Uzbekistan provides a comprehensive framework for the rights and responsibilities of employers and employees, ensuring worker protection and promoting fair and equitable working conditions.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2012. – 40 б.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Меҳнат кодекси: (2010 йил 1 мартгача бўлган ўзгартиш ва қўшимчалар билан) Расмий нашр. – Т.: Адолат, 2010. – 276 б.
3. Иноятов А. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг меҳнат ҳуқуқи: Дарслик. – Т.: Иқтисодиёт ва ҳуқуқ дунёси, 2002.
4. Одилқориев Х.Т., Тультеев И.Т. ва бошқ. Давлат ва ҳуқуқ назарияси: Дарслик. – Т.: «Sharq», 2009
5. Турсунов Й. Меҳнат ҳуқуқи: Дарслик. – Т.: Молия, 2002